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Calculation of power savings via a frequency converter in linter equipment of a cotton ginning and linting workshop

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Abstract. This paper examines the properties of cotton fiber, the production of secondary products from cottonseed, and the machinery used in the cotton ginning industry, with emphasis on the role and utilization of electric motors. It also discusses European experiences with linter technologies in cotton ginning enterprises and considerations of cotton cultivation in other countries. The potential energy-saving effect of installing variable-frequency drives (frequency converters) on the electric motors of ginning and linter machines is analyzed.

Keywords: cotton fiber; cottonseed; electric motor; linting; cotton ginning machinery; frequency converter; energy efficiency; rectifier; filter; cluster enterprise; rotational speed.

Расчет экономии электроэнергии за счет преобразователя частоты в линтерном оборудовании хлопкоочистительного и линтоочистительного цеха

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются свойства хлопкового волокна, производство вторичных продуктов из хлопкового семени и машины, используемые в хлопкоочистительной промышленности, с акцентом на роль и использование электродвигателей. Также обсуждается европейский опыт применения линтерных технологий на хлопкоочистительных предприятиях и особенности выращивания хлопка в других странах. Анализируется потенциальный энергосберегающий эффект установки частотно-регулируемых приводов (преобразователей частоты) на электродвигателях хлопкоочистительных и линтоочистительных машин.

Ключевые слова: хлопковое волокно; хлопковое семя; электродвигатель; линтер; хлопкоочистительное оборудование; преобразователь частоты; энергоэффективность; выпрямитель; фильтр; кластерное предприятие; скорость вращения.

Paxta tolasi va chigitini tozalash sexining linter uskunasi- da chastota konvertori hisobiga energiya tejashni hisoblash

Dalibekov Lochinbek Rustambekovich, Maripova Mashrabxon Davlatjon qizi

Farg'ona davlat texnika universiteti

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada paxta tolasining xossalari, paxta chigitidan ikkilamchi mahsulot olish, paxta tozalash sanoatida qo'llaniladigan mashinalar haqida so'z yuritilib, elektr motorlarining roli va qo'llanilishiga alohida to'xtalib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, paxta tozalash zavodlarida linter texnologiyalarini qo'llash bo'yicha Yevropa tajribasi va boshqa mamlakatlarda paxta yetishtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ham muhokama qilinadi. Paxta tozalash va paxta tozalash mashinalarining elektr motorlariga o'zgaruvchan chastotali uzatgichlarni (chastota o'zgartirgichlar) o'rnatishning potentsial energiya tejovchi ta'siri tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: paxta tolasi; paxta chigiti; elektr motor; linter; paxta tozalash uskunalari; chastota konvertori; energiya samaradorligi; rektifikator; filtr; klaster korxonasi; aylanish tezligi.

Introduction

Uzbekistan is a major producer of cotton fiber, which is the primary raw material for the country's textile and light industries. The competitiveness of the cotton products on the world market depends on their quality meeting standard requirements and international norms. To ensure high product quality, cotton processing enterprises perform several key operations: they receive and store raw cotton, feed it into the initial processing line, and produce end products such as cotton fiber (lint), cottonseed, and short fiber (linters). The core stages of the primary processing technology include:

- Drying seed cotton.
- Cleaning seed cotton from fine and coarse impurities.
- Ginning (separating cotton fibers from the seeds).
- Linting (removing residual fibers from the seeds).
- Cleaning and compressing the fiber, linters, and fiber waste into bales.
- Preparing cottonseed for sowing.

These processes require separating the fiber from the seed and obtaining secondary products. An effective method for saving electrical power in the ginning and linter machines of the fiber separation and secondary-product recovery system is to install an automatic frequency control device (variable-frequency drive) on the electric motor of the ginning and linter machine. This approach can significantly reduce energy consumption while maintaining process quality.

Electric Motors and Variable-Frequency Drives in Cotton Processing

Induction (asynchronous) electric motors are widely used in industrial applications. In developed countries, nearly half of all generated electrical energy is consumed by electric motors, and over 90% of these motors are of the induction type. For a long time, electric motors were primarily used in applications requiring a fixed rotor speed. However, in the past few decades, rapid advances in high-power electronics and converter technologies have made it possible to efficiently control motor speed by varying the supply frequency. This development has led to the emergence of variable-frequency induction motors. Using frequency converters (inverters) together with electric motors offers advantages over other speed-control methods.

The main advantages of variable-frequency drives include:

- **Smooth speed regulation:** They allow continuous and precise control of the motor's rotor speed.
- **Soft starting:** They enable gradual, stress-free motor starts, reducing mechanical and electrical stress.
- **High dynamic performance:** They maintain high stiffness in the motor's mechanical characteristics while achieving high efficiency in electromagnetic excitation.

A typical frequency converter system consists of a rectifier stage, a DC filter element, an inverter stage, and a control system. In the rectifier stage, usually implemented with a diode bridge, the AC supply voltage is converted into a pulsating DC voltage. The filter element then smooths out the ripples in the rectified DC voltage. The inverter stage takes this DC voltage and converts it into a three-phase AC output. Commonly, the inverter power stage is a three-phase bridge built from six IGBT power transistors (with bidirectional conduction).

The control system regulates the output frequency by generating control signals for the inverter. In practice, the control input is transformed into a series of gate pulses applied to the inverter's IGBT transistors. By adjusting the timing and width of these pulses, the system can control both the amplitude and frequency of the output voltage. In this way, the voltage supplied to the motor can be adjusted in accordance with the available DC bus voltage (determined by the rectifier output).

Modern static frequency converters typically use pulse-width modulation (PWM). The efficiency of state-of-the-art inverters is on the order of 95%. However, the PWM process introduces higher-order harmonic components into the output waveform. These additional harmonics can negatively affect the motor's performance and efficiency. In effect, the inverter alters the motor's characteristics and can introduce noise into the power supply network. The increased harmonic content mainly

causes higher copper (I^2R) losses in the motor windings, leading to an elevated motor temperature and a reduction in motor efficiency. Studies have shown that the overall efficiency (performance) of equipment connected through an inverter may decrease under these conditions. Therefore, investigating the efficiency of an induction motor when powered via an inverter is an important task for understanding the net benefits of variable-frequency drives.

Energy Savings through Frequency Control

In general, using a frequency converter to control an electric motor can save a substantial amount of energy compared to traditional fixed-speed control methods. It is often cited that a variable-frequency drive can reduce energy consumption by at least 30%. For example, simply reducing the motor's supply frequency by 20% (from 50 Hz down to 40 Hz) can halve the power consumption under certain load conditions. This relationship is roughly demonstrated by the affinity laws for fans and pumps, where power varies with the cube of the speed, though the exact savings depend on the process requirements.

Consider a practical example in the cotton ginning and linting workshop. Suppose the linter machine has ten electric motors, each rated at 22 kW. If all ten motors run at full load, the total power consumption is 220 kW (10×22 kW) per hour. By installing the proposed frequency converter on these motors, a 20% reduction in power usage is achievable (i.e., each motor saves 4.4 kW). For the entire set of ten motors (five pairs of linter units), this corresponds to a total savings of 44 kW per hour.

If the total hourly power consumption of the entire initial cotton processing enterprise is 1800 kW, then saving 44 kW per hour amounts to about 2% of the facility's energy usage. Implementing similar frequency-converter installations in other production sections could further increase the plant's overall energy savings.

Thus, retrofitting ginning and linter machines with variable-frequency drives presents a viable strategy for reducing electricity consumption in cotton processing.

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